

POLICY BRIEF COMMON TEMPLATE OPERAS-PLUS AND ITS EFFORTS FOR BRIDGING RESEARCH&SOCIETY

INTRODUCTION:

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02

(Developing and consolidating the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership (2021))

TOPIC: [OPERAS-PLUS and its efforts for bridging research & society](#)

PROJECT: On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure (OPERAS-PLUS)
<https://operas-eu.org>

PROJECT: objectives

The general objective of the OPERAS-PLUS project is to provide the necessary support OPERAS needs to complete its preparatory phase and to transition its status into an ERIC.

This general objective is divided in several specific objectives (SOs), defined by the topic description, the recommendations provided by the ESFRI report and the issues raised by the OPERAS General Assembly in 2021:

(SO1) To develop and strengthen OPERAS governance structure, esp. financial, legal, and human resource management aspects of the infrastructure central hub in a sustainable way, compliant with RI management best practices.

(SO2) To support the establishment and development of OPERAS national nodes, set up and manage their relations with the central hub.

(SO3) To develop OPERAS portfolio of services by providing both required technology and a monitoring system for services development.

(SO4) To maximise OPERAS' impact in the ERA and at international level by extending it beyond its current scope and onboarding new members and countries in the infrastructure.

Name and email address of the operational project coordinator:

Michael Kaiser, Max Weber Stiftung, kaiser@maxweberstiftung.de

POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Research and society relationships cover many forms of collaborations, ranging from R&D endeavors between public research institutions and private enterprises to participatory practices such as citizen science. Across this broad spectrum, there are two crucial elements of the collaboration that require special attention: the accessibility of research outputs and meaningful public engagement. As a research infrastructure specialised in Open Access and inclusive governance, OPERAS is well positioned to inform policies that aim to strengthen the relationship between research and society.

OPERAS RI: Advancing Open Scholarly Communication in SSH

[OPERAS Research Infrastructure](#) (OPERAS RI) is dedicated to fostering open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). It supports direct communication through the blogging platform [Hypotheses](#), facilitates discoverability and open access to research

publications and data through [GoTriple](#), provides services such as [PRISM](#) (a peer review tool) and [Pathfinder](#) (a catalogue of Open Access publishing services), and it facilitates coordinated efforts for the [European Diamond Capacity Hub](#) (EDCH). OPERAS RI also actively promotes citizen science practices as an essential pillar of open science in SSH: it recently launched the [VERA](#) platform, a digital hub where researchers and society members meet and collaborate.

Collaboration and governance: enabling systemic change

OPERAS believes that systemic change in scholarly communication requires collaborative governance and genuine dialogue between research and society — not merely one-way dissemination from academia. As a mission-driven research infrastructure, OPERAS RI integrates collaborative practices, shared governance and co-creation approaches in both its innovation efforts and policy advocacy. Not only are the services co-designed with the OPERAS members and the larger engaged community, but also a shared vision is built through initiatives like the OPERAS [living book](#), a common place for the involved bodies and their members, to shape altogether the common OPERAS vision.

Governance is a clear demonstration of this commitment. OPERAS brings together representatives from three of the four quadrants of the quadruple helix — Academia, Industry, and Policy. Its governance bodies include:

- ❖ Executive Assembly: Composed of core members (RPOs and RFOs), it guides strategic development.
- ❖ General Assembly: Includes ministries, infrastructures, and elected representatives; it approves annual plans and budgets.
- ❖ Assembly of the Commons (AoC): Gathers ordinary members — such as libraries, publishers, SMEs, and RIs — who work in
- ❖ Special Interest Groups (SIGs).
- ❖ Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) and Service and Technology Board (STB): Provide expert guidance and strategic insight.

This collaborative governance model enables OPERAS to foster systemic change across a complex, multi-stakeholder scholarly communication landscape. A recent example of this in practice is OPERAS' central role in co-developing the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) in close collaboration with the Diamond Open Access European community.

Caring about community engagement at all levels

A variety of institutions, representing diverse stakeholders (researchers, librarians, policy makers, publishers...) actively participate in the OPERAS decision-making process through the Executive Assembly, making each key step taken by OPERAS a result of a collaborative decision. The OPERAS Special Interest Groups (SIGs) are also key channels for community engagement, as all ordinary members are required to join at least one. Due to their nature, the SIGs are a privileged environment to listen to the community's needs. Such needs and challenges can then be addressed by OPERAS through project proposals and developing new services. Their work and discussions are presented to the Assembly of the Commons (AoC), the governance body that gathers all Ordinary Members annually to suggest the infrastructure's direction and propose topics for the General Assembly. In addition, OPERAS has 13 National Nodes (NNs), which work as bridges between OPERAS and the national communities, sharing best practices, promoting multilingualism and enabling engagement and transformation at the national level.

OPERAS improves its services based on community engagement including feedback from the SIGs; reporting issues directly in each service platform; participating in online surveys; taking part in online or in-person usability tests, focus groups and workshops (e.g. Mutual Learning Exercises, Researcher Forums). Community participation is a cornerstone of OPERAS-PLUS and other projects, where diverse stakeholders have an active voice on topics important to OPERAS and the broader European Research Area, particularly in areas such as the Diamond Open Access Model and the Research Assessment Reform (COARA).

Enhancing Outreach, Innovation, Knowledge Transfer and Civil Society Engagement

OPERAS Research Infrastructure supports and enhances the discoverability, visibility, accessibility, and reuse of SSH research through a [catalog of dedicated, interoperable services](#), aligned to the FAIR principles. These services facilitate dissemination and provide the conditions necessary for meaningful outreach and engagement, ensuring that diverse audiences can discover, access, understand, and reuse research.

This enabling approach is exemplified by platforms such as [GoTriple](#), which offers advanced tools for multilingual discovery and visualisation of SSH research. These tools are designed to support not only researchers but also societal actors and private sector stakeholders, helping them navigate the SSH knowledge landscape, identify expertise, and connect with relevant communities and projects.

In a context where research infrastructures are expected to foster stronger links with society, the [VERA platform](#) provides a concrete, operational example of how digital services can scale participatory research practices while maintaining alignment with scientific quality, equity, and openness: VERA is indeed a digital hub to support participatory and citizen science projects in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), including a multilingual interface, matchmaking tools, project management support, and access to tailored funding opportunities. As part of the OPERAS service portfolio, VERA directly contributes to EU policy goals related to open science, public engagement, and inclusive research practices. Both GoTriple and the VERA platform have been developed in collaboration with a SME.

Finally, the OPERAS [Innovation Lab](#) plays an important role in sustaining the outreach and innovation ecosystem. The Lab combines an Observatory that gathers insights on emerging trends with an Accelerator that supports the development and piloting of community-driven ideas. By supporting agile experimentation, the Lab helps to bridge gaps between academic knowledge and societal needs, enabling a real dialogue, while working closely with various OPERAS bodies, members, and external partners to co-create scalable and relevant solutions.

Recommendations:

The following recommendations derive from the practices and insights detailed in the previous sections, including OPERAS' multi-level governance model, mechanisms for community engagement, and service-oriented platforms. Together, these examples illustrate how participatory, inclusive, and co-designed approaches can shape a research infrastructure that is both socially relevant and operationally sustainable. To support and expand the OPERAS approach across Europe, the following actions are recommended:

1. Ensure long-term operational support for participatory research infrastructures, including service maintenance and dedicated human resources such as community managers;
2. Encourage funder engagement through co-designed tools and shared programme spaces within platforms like VERA;
3. Adapt funding schemes to better accommodate participatory research formats, community-driven co-design approaches, and the specific needs of SSH-driven citizen science;
4. Promote inclusive evaluation frameworks, such as co-evaluation and participatory assessment models, suitable for community-engaged research;
5. Foster communication and interaction around societal challenges through integrated discussion spaces and collaborative thematic hubs;
6. Enable and incentivise cross-sectoral funding collaborations, including public-private-philanthropic partnerships, to ensure long-term sustainability;
7. Support innovation through funding schemes allowing the scaling of projects and mentoring approaches.